

Trending Tracks for Eye Movement Behaviour on Webpages Using Mobile Application

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Abstract:

In most usability and user experience tests, eye movement is one of the major components of user perception study. The user eye tracking makes it easier and possible to record the eye movement positions by analysing in both Mobile 2-Dimensional and 3-Dimensional virtual environments. The process is to gather insight into the user's mind and mind processes by revealing more than one can imagine. The mobile eye movement can help understand how users feel, think, and act about certain objects and subjects in the visual field. Most research used quantitative data from mobile-based eye tracking on image and video content to help complement studies through questionnaires and surveys; traditional eye movement studies have been known to capture remote and mobile eye trackers through confined lab studies and some of these analysis has proved tedious. This paper seeks to investigate the trends in mobile eye movement studies, by generating users' data through interaction with webpage dynamic contents. The data generated underwent a post-analysis by simulating the effect and eye movement on e-learning webpages, the patterns observed are seen to be synchronous in behaviour with both original and simulated fixation patterns on the webpages they visited; this also shows the authenticity of using simulated eye movement behaviour for decision making.

Keywords: Mobile eye tracking, Fixation patterns, User experience, Usability testing, Webpage dynamic content, Saccades

1 Introduction

Research has seen that eye-tracking methods are a measure of people's perception of what they look at and how long they spend looking at what they view. This process has become accessible to user experience (UX) research design procedures due to its technological improvement. Researchers can now observe users' eyes and obtain more insights about their visual attention. This paper explores the latest trends in eye movement studies and how the advanced methodology can be included in the UX research mobile toolbox. The advanced method used in eye movement studies can be very valuable for both usability and UX testing since it can record the journey without actually interfering with the users' natural behaviour instinct. For instance when a test prototype is conducted and it is discovered that the participants were not interacting with the widgets in the manner they were not supposed to, the next thought that comes to mind is that the controls and buttons are tiny and one would need to change the visual aesthetics, position, and colour. And as a result of this, the controls might be made prominent which would still not serve their purpose.

The extensive investigation would disclose findings that users don't see some of these controls even though they are visible to them, they don't know how to use them. The user of an eye-tracking device can help the research method in observing the lack of comprehension of these widgets and its display and mobile eye-tracking now play a very important role in eye movement navigation study. It is similar to seeing through the users' minds, recognising the usability problem in an instant, and even users' emotional response which would save clients and developers time and budget resources. Eye movement studies provide information that allows one to know how people navigate on a webpage and how they are drawn to visual aesthetics [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. The process of how easy and intuitive it is in task completion can be more explicit for mobile app design and usability testing. Different ambiguous mobile design techniques can boost UX which would inspire mobile designers on clever ways and solutions to tackle confirmation dialogues, video content, mobile navigation, and gamifying the user waiting experience.

The use of mobile user experience has doubled over the past decade and indicates the current trends on how valuable mobile web design can be used to improve user experience. Numerous web design experiments in current times are adopted by different companies, this includes trends such as non-traditional webpage layouts, improved accessibility in dark mode, and the infamous parallax visual scrolling. These methods have still not reached their highest exploration if the trend is broken out of track. The benefit the most from this study tracks hidden design gems that correspond to navigation, dialogue confirmation waiting experience needs to be divulged (Figure 1). Those methods might be unconventional the main point could be valuable and design procedures will be built with the main pillars of accessibility in usability, this can also be refined to fit the ultimate goal of convenient user interaction and experience. Also, some of these approaches can be creative by combining elegant design and functionality like the smashing online workshop on a front-end interaction for user experience with live video sessions and an online friendly survey on questions and answers (Q&A). The following section discusses pathways in eye movement tracking for usability testing.

Figure 1: Navigation and dialogue confirmation of waiting experience on mobile phones (Courtesy: Google images).

2 Literature Review

In eye-tracking evolution, the first moment a person conducted a study on usability is by observing the movement of the eyes through direct observation during the early 1800s [14, 15], since that moment, eye-tracking technology has evolved. The beginning of naked-eye observation became a sophisticated and realistic accurate technology that measures eye movements [9, 10, 11, 12, 13]. Eye tracking is an innovation, but recent findings in the technology have made the methods accessible to both commercial and user computer interaction processes of all sizes.

During the late 1990s [16, 17], both advertising and marketing agencies saw the basic potential of eye-tracking for

the web and began using technology as analytics on how users consume content online. The few advertising commercial companies that used eye-tracking during that period were the EURO RSCG & Partners. These companies utilise eye movement methods to measure all aspects of visual attention of both dynamic and static banners, navigational tools in webpages, and animated graphics. Webpages were designed as printed media before those studies, with justified columns and a large block of text content. The Yahoo pages in early 1997 are a simple example of the process of how webpages were less based on dynamic controls and assumed the structure of a vivid printed newspaper form. The implementation of eye-tracking provided useful insight into how to help shape the work of web developers and designers. Neilson's research [[18, 19]] showed how people read content on the internet in the form of an "F-shaped pattern" where the users tend to begin reading the content from top to left. The next stage was moving their eyes from the top to the right section of a page by skimming through the basic contents that stood out like the images and subtle subheadings. The visual representation of these eye movements was made by heatmaps on the F-shaped pattern that showcases the relevance of eye-tracking in creating guidelines to write for web design pages.

Current times have seen the fact that hardware and software are given design styles to perform eye movement behaviour controls for psychological, medical, and gaming research and also including marketing and UX. Eye movement studies are used in marketing to test advertising product placement, and control location and packaging for visual attention. The context of virtual reality is another area that has been reflecting huge potential in eye movement behaviour tracking. The use of a VR headset can help to see where the users are looking and how to make the experience a significant immersive invention. The PC gaming eye-tracking [20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26] can also allow the user to look at objects that they desire to interact with and press controls instead of the mouse to guide them to the widgets they navigate. The user of web forms is now at the center of expressive user interaction, and this requires a steady handle. Recently various forms of design patterns have been useful for practical guides to building and designing web widgets and controls. Most of these designs are studied through eye movement with more focus on the saccadic movement.

The saccade is the rapid and ballistic movements of the eyes that can abruptly change within a point focus of fixation, they also range in amplitude from a tiny movement caused by reading. The saccades can be elicited both subtly and voluntarily; this can occur in a reflex action when both eyes are open and fixated on the target object. The time interval of a saccadic eye movement (Figure 2) is the onset from a target object to response amplitude. It takes about 200ms for the eye movement to commence.

Figure 2: Components of saccadic eye movement on target object and positions..

The smooth pursuit of eye movements a slow in tracking in keeping track of a moving stimulus, they are based on voluntary control where the observer can select the option of choosing a moving stimulus. The saccades are also voluntary eye movements but the difference lies in the unconscious action. Highly trained observers can make a smooth pursuit in the absence of any moving target object and a saccade can be made on most people who decide to move their eyes in a smooth fashion rather than a swift saccadic movement. Figure 3 shows the common metrics for smooth pursuit eye movement with blue lines as eye movements that track stimulus moving at a constant velocity that matches

the target movement.

Figure 3: Common metrics for smooth pursuit eye movement with blue lines as eye movements.

Compensatory eye movements are due to the activation of smooth pursuit systems that rely mostly on visual cues that indicate the motion of the visual field rather than vestibular information. For instance, if one wants to measure where a person is looking and how they visually scan the visual environment, smooth eye movement is the best procedure or choice of method to obtain any valuable information. The process of looking is based on automatic visibility and can be used in qualitative as well as quantitative research help researchers to tap into the non-conscious processes which govern the normal biases of surfing preferences.

Figure 4: Area of interest (AOI) set in a selected region of E-learning webpages.

3 Method

Predefined data from a previous experimental study on usability on a mobile webpage app was used for this analysis and contains an informative feature that can be applied for a wide range of research purposes that could also include psychological and perceptual studies on webpage design and product preferences. The dataset contains information about user browsing behaviour that includes fixations and gaze points, area of interest (AOI), time to the first fixation, time spent on the target object, fixation sequences, fixation duration, and average fixation duration. The area of interest (AOI) is the selected region (Figure 4 of the displayed stimulus on the mobile webpage app and is used to extract metrics for user experience components and defines the area in which others like the scan-path, saccade, and fixation duration are calculated. The webpage content used for the stimulus display consists of dynamic and static web controls where users have to surf online for information about the website (“*ui.org*” and “*zyro.com*”), the participants have to navigate between this two websites provided for them. The cognitive states of the users were based on six (6) different arousal states depending on the set metric of the pupil response using Table 1 and how much time passed from the stimulus onset till the participants looked at the given AOI. The number of fixations counted is synchronised with the way the participants looked away from the AOI or off-screen. The process comes in handy when evaluating the performance of the gaze metrics in more than one area of interest. A single webpage may contain more than one navigation page and still use the same allocated AOI. The eye movement behaviour is recorded in synchronous to the webpages the user visited with pupil changes recorded with a mapped fixation on both the *X* and *Y* Cartesian plane of the website stimulus. The proceeding section discusses some of the resulting output obtained from the analysis.

Table 1: Metrics for determining the cognitive response correlates to pupil response

S/No.	Fixation range	Cognitive state	Pupil measure
1	250 - 300	Average	Constriction
2.	350 - 400	Complex	Dilation
3.	450 - 600	Neutral	Dilation
4	650 - 800	Relaxed	Constriction
5	850 - 900	Stress	Dilation

4 Result

The fixations and saccades displayed on the mobile webpages are the basic output measures of the interest and these are often the most used parameters in the measurements. The gaze points can show what the users are looking at at a particular point in time. The analysis displayed here shows this process in chronologies with the pupil changes in both dilation and constriction metrics to the cognitive response of the users and the web address they visited. Figure 5 shows the aggregate response of the participants to the website”*ui.org*”, this is based on a sampling rate of 60Hz per second for the series of gaze points that looks so close together, that the gaze cluster constitutes the fixation denoting the period where the eyes looked towards the web dynamic contents on the page and represents an excellent measure for both visual attention and cognitive response. The saccades a the eye movements between fixations, the eyes don’t travel smoothly when the intention is to read the content but rather they look towards every 6-8 letter content depending on the size of the text content it reads. The visual span is higher and covers more text content with few fixations The fixations points are directed towards the image content relative to other parts of the webpage AOI and show that the more the fixations the more visual attention has been directed to the assigned AOI. Sometimes is very difficult to decipher if the fixations involve the spatial distribution of eye movement in a particular area. It can also provide a starting for visual comprehension about the aspect of a scene that is best captured that sustains attention.

Figure 6 shows the time to the first fixation indicates the amount of time that it takes for the participant to look at a specific area of interest from the stimulus onset. It indicates both the Button-up stimulus search that correlates to the search engine point of interest and a top-down attention search where the participant focuses on certain elements of the webpage picture content. This is a basic form of search behaviour and a valuable metric in eye movement behaviour tracking that provides information about how certain search items on an online study website are prioritised on mobile webpage applications. A time spent on dwell time frames helps to quantify the amount of time that a user has spent looking at certain AOI, a relative increase in the time spent on part of the search engine is associated with the motives and the top-down attention of the user as they refrain from looking at other visual content that could be termed as equally interesting. The long duration while looking at the search point indicates a high level of visual

(a) Fixation and saccades made by use eye movement on "iu.org"

(b) Web address correlates to pupil response and fixations on X and Y Cartesian plane

Figure 5: Aggregate response of the participants to the website "iu.org"

interest and the emotional reaction to that visual scene can also be derived by a physiological measuring sensor, which also the pupil dilation can represent in this case. Figure 6b indicates a synchronous increase in amplitude for both

pupil changes and the mapped fixation on the X and Y Cartesian plain of the webpage which correlates with the onset of the "www.zyro.com" webpage to "ui.org" first page.

(a) Fixation and saccades made by user eye movement on "ui.org" and "zyro.com"

(b) Web address correlates to pupil response and fixations on X and Y Cartesian plane

Figure 6: Aggregate response of the participants to the website "ui.org" and "zyro.com"

These metrics provide information about how many of the users guided their gaze towards certain AOI, this might also be relevant to optimise search patterns and aesthetics so that more customers are drawn towards the desired region that could be in the form of a picture content or icon the leads the user to the desired search result. The last fixation sequence often leads to a more predictive choice of content such as leading the evaluators to conclude that left-right and top-bottom reading could be based on assumptions that readers are particularly conclusive in their search behaviour pattern by a simple off-screen view. The revisits can also indicate how many times a user returned their gaze to the object of interest defined by the AOI and allow an evaluator to examine which of the contents repeated attracts them. The fixation duration provides information about the amount of time spent on that point and the increase in dilation of the pupil response also indicates a complex cognitive response in reaction to their browsing habit at that particular point in time.

5 Conclusion

This paper seeks to investigate the mobile-based trending tracks for eye movement behaviour on dynamic webpages, data generated from a predefined experiment saved in an archive underwent a post-analysis by simulating the effect and eye movement on an online E-learning webpage, and the patterns observed are seen to be synchronous in behaviour with both original and simulated fixation patterns made by the cognitive response of the users in form pupil changes on the webpages they visited; this also shows the authenticity of using simulated eye movement behaviour for decision making and the future use of pupil response as a cognitive representation of user behaviour and emotional response to the contents they viewed. The future perspective would be to integrate biosensors in synch with eye movements to be able to simulate and give an authentic description of the emotional response of the users that matches their behaviour search pattern. It would also tell more about a fixation point on visual stimulus rather than what the user is simply looking at; that is, by looking at a fixation we can be able to interpret the emotions related to the fixation and the fixation sequence.

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